

Figure 5I: PS6 Film

P S6 3.23.18

Figure 5I Arrows indicate lanes used in figure

Lane 1: Sib-3 Veh, Lane 2: Sib-3 SC-79 (2ug/mL), Lane 3: Sib-3: Sc-79 (6ug/mL), Lane 4: Sib-3: MK-2206 (30nM)
Lane 5: I-ASD-3 Veh Lane 6: I-ASD-3 SC-79 (2ug/mL), Lane 7: I-ASD-3 SC-79 (6ug/mL), Lane 8: I-ASD-3 MK-2206 (30nM)
Lane 9: Sib-3 C1, NI1, Lane 10, Sib-3 C2, NI1, Lane 11: Sib-3 C2, NI2

Bold text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

Figure 5I: GAPDH for PS6 Film

Phospha

Gapdh #

3.27.18

Figure 5I Arrows indicate lanes used in figure

Lane 1: Sib-3 Veh, Lane 2: Sib-3 SC-79 (2ug/mL) , Lane 3: Sib-3: Sc-79 (6ug/mL), Lane 4: Sib-3: MK-2206 (30nM)
Lane 5: I-ASD-3 Veh Lane 6: I-ASD-3 SC-79 (2ug/mL), Lane 7: I-ASD-3 SC-79 (6ug/mL), Lane 8: I-ASD-3 MK-2206 (30nM)
Lane 9: Sib-3 C1, NI1, Lane 10, Sib-3 C2, NI1, Lane 11: Sib-3 C2, NI2

Bold text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

#2
✓

#3
✓

Figure 5I: Total S6 Film

Total S6 3.23.18

Figure 5I Arrows indicate lanes used in figure

Lane 1: Sib-3 Veh, Lane 2: Sib-3 SC-79 (2ug/mL), Lane 3: Sib-3: Sc-79 (6ug/mL), Lane 4: Sib-3: MK-2206 (30nM)
Lane 5: I-ASD-3 Veh Lane 6: I-ASD-3 SC-79 (2ug/mL), Lane 7: I-ASD-3 SC-79 (6ug/mL), Lane 8: I-ASD-3 MK-2206 (30nM)
Lane 9: Sib-3 C1, NI1, Lane 10, Sib-3 C2, NI1, Lane 11: Sib-3 C2, NI2

Bold text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

Figure 5I: GAPDH for
Total S6 Film

Total
GAPDH

3.27.18

Figure 5I

Arrows indicate lanes used in figure

Lane 1: Sib-3 Veh, Lane 2: Sib-3 SC-79 (2ug/mL), Lane 3: Sib-3: Sc-79 (6ug/mL), Lane 4: Sib-3: MK-2206 (30nM)
Lane 5: I-ASD-3 Veh Lane 6: I-ASD-3 SC-79 (2ug/mL), Lane 7: I-ASD-3 SC-79 (6ug/mL), Lane 8: I-ASD-3 MK-2206 (30nM)
Lane 9: Sib-3 C1, NI1, Lane 10, Sib-3 C2, NI1, Lane 11: Sib-3 C2, NI2

Bold text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

#2 ✓

#3 ✓